

A Comparative study of Functional outcomes in PFN versus PFNA for Fixation of Unstable Intertrochanteric FracturePrashant Kumar Sharma¹, J Jerin Tamil Valan², Sanjay Dev³, Rijin PS⁴¹Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Rama Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh²Postgraduate, Department of Orthopaedics, Rama Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh³Postgraduate, Department of Orthopaedics, Rama Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh⁴Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Rama Medical College Hospital & Research Centre, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract:**Background:** Unstable intertrochanteric fractures poses challenges in terms of obtaining stable fixation and good postoperative outcomes. There is a paucity of clinical data comparing the commonly used Proximal Femoral Nail (PFN) and Proximal Femoral Nail Antirotation (PFNA) implants, especially in relation to osteoporosis.**Objective:** To assess comparative performance of PFN and PFNA fixation in the treatment of unstable femur intertrochanteric fractures.**Methods:** This study was conducted from November 2021 to October 2023 at Department of Orthopedics, in a tertiary care center located in northern India. Patients presenting with unstable intertrochanteric were included and treated with either PFN or PFNA. Boyd and Griffin classification type 2, 3 and 4 were included. A proximal femoral nail was used to treat all fractures. At the follow-ups, all patients were evaluated using the Modified Harris Hip Score. Patients were followed up for a minimum of 6 months and any complications noted. Comparison of functional outcomes was done using the Harris Hip Score. Statistical analysis was done using the unpaired t-test/Mann-Whitney U test and Chi-square test/Fisher's-exact test. A p-value of < 0.05 was considered significant.**Results:** Every follow-up period included a Harris hip score assessment. At 3 months, the average score of PFN was 71.9 (range 66-81) and at 6 months it was 77.86 (range 72-90). For PFNA, at 3 months the average score was 74.87 (range 66-81) and at 6 months, it was 89.3 (range 76-94). The improvement was seen well in PFNA group which is statistically significant (p=0.023). The most prevalent fracture was a type 2 fracture.**Conclusion:** The results showed PFNA has better rotation stability with single screw and better functional outcome in treating unstable intertrochanteric fractures when compared to PFN.**Keywords:** Proximal Femoral Nail, Unstable Trochanteric fracture, Lateral trochanteric wall, Communicated fragments.

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Introduction

In modern era due to increasing life expectancy and declining fertility rates, a change towards ageing population is being witnessed all over world and in India too. And it is expected to grow more in coming decades. [1, 2] Proximal femoral fractures are a major cause of morbidity and mortality world over in view of huge population, high road traffic accident rate and increasing age of population.[3] According to Gulberg et al., fractures around hip will reach 2.6 million by 2025 and 4.5 million by 2050.[4] Intertrochanteric fractures accounted for

26% of all hip fractures in Asia in 1990, but this number is expected to climb to 37% in 2025 and 45 percent in 2050.[5] The intertrochanteric region of the femur, rich in cancellous bone, is susceptible to stress fractures, especially in older adults. The cancellous bone in the intertrochanteric region becomes increasingly vulnerable with age, primarily as a result of osteoporosis, particularly in postmenopausal women. In younger adults, intertrochanteric fractures are often caused by high-energy trauma such as road traffic accidents or falls

from heights. The intertrochanteric area of the femur is vulnerable in such scenarios due to its position as the mechanical link between the femoral shaft and the femoral neck.[6] Conservative treatment for inter-trochanteric fracture femur is not a very recommended option as these fracture associated with high complication rates like mal-union with coxa-vara, external rotation, greater trochanter up riding and abductor muscle insufficiency leading to gait disturbances,[7] so now it's recommended to treat these fracture surgically to establish a stable fixation that enables patients to be mobilised sooner, avoiding the difficulties that come with extended immobility. Extra medullary and intramedullary implants may be utilised to repair these fractures, however intramedullary implants provide better biological fixing and are load-sharing devices.

Extra medullary devices are always under stress due to bending strain, which is bad for fractures, but intramedullary devices are under axial strain. A study indicated that functional outcomes were markedly better for patients of the intramedullary nail group when compared with those of the extramedullary fixation group ($p = 0.0028$).[8] But intra-medullary device like conventional PFN also have dis-advantages like risk of neck screw back-out, cut throw, Z-effect, reverse Z-effect especially when the bone quality is not optimum. In the view of these drawback this device modified, and PFN-A has made. Recent evidence-based medicine studies suggest that cephalon-medullary nailing using PFN-A is superior to PFN in terms of a lesser procedure time, minimal blood loss, and fewer complications even among osteoporotic patients.[9] The objective of surgical treatment for an intertrochanteric fracture is to return the patient to their pre-injury condition as soon as feasible. Internal fixation of these fractures was used to improve patient comfort, enable nursing care, shorten hospitalisation, and lessen the problems associated with extended recumbency.[10] The goal of this research is to compare the functional and radiological outcomes of PFN and PFNA fixation in the treatment of femur intertrochanteric fractures that are unstable.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted on patients who underwent surgery between November 2021 and October 2023 in the Department of Orthopedics at a tertiary care center in northern India. Patients included in the study were above 18 years of age, had radiological evidence confirming unstable intertrochanteric fractures, and were classified under Boyd and Griffin types II, III, and IV. Only those who were medically fit and willing to undergo surgery were considered. Patients were excluded if they had Boyd and Griffin type I

fractures, fractures extending into the diaphysis, compound fractures, or pathological fractures. A total of 50 patients with unstable intertrochanteric fractures were treated using either proximal femoral nail (PFN) or proximal femoral nail antirotation (PFNA). Among them, 25 patients underwent fixation with PFN, while the other 25 underwent fixation with PFNA. All surgeries were performed at a single center by the same team of surgeons. Follow-up assessments were conducted at 6 weeks, 3 months, and 6 months post-surgery, with radiological and clinical evaluations performed during each visit using the Modified Harris Hip Score.

All patients included in the study were admitted through the emergency department, presenting with complaints of pain in the affected hip and/or other body parts following trauma caused either by a fall or a road traffic accident (RTA). Each patient underwent a comprehensive evaluation, including routine investigations. The diagnosis was based on clinical findings and radiological examinations, with X-rays of the pelvis (anteroposterior views of both hips) and lateral views of the affected hip being sufficient for diagnosis. Patients who met the inclusion and exclusion criteria were enrolled in the study.

The patients were divided into two groups using simple randomization: Group A consisted of those treated with PFN, while Group B comprised those treated with PFNA2. All patients underwent a pre-anesthetic evaluation, and surgery was performed as early as possible once they were deemed fit for the procedure. During surgery, intraoperative parameters such as blood loss and duration (from skin incision to closure) were recorded.

Postoperative follow-ups were conducted at 6 weeks, 3 months, and 6 months. Functional assessments were performed at each follow-up visit, and a final evaluation was carried out at 6 months using the Modified Harris Hip Score.

Results

In this study involving 50 patients with unstable intertrochanteric fractures, 25 patients were treated with proximal femoral nail antirotation (PFNA) and 25 with proximal femoral nail (PFN). The results showed that most patients belonged to the age group of 40–49 years. The mean age of patients treated with PFN was 47.21 years, while that of PFNA patients was 47.1 years, with no statistically significant difference between the two groups.

Regarding gender distribution, among the PFN group, 18 out of 25 patients were male and 7 were female. Similarly, in the PFNA group, 16 out of 25 patients were male and 9 were female. In both groups, the right hip was predominantly affected. Most patients in both groups sustained injuries due

to a trivial fall, with 52% of the total study population reporting accidental falls and 48% reporting road traffic accidents (RTA) as the cause of injury.

The fracture types, as classified by Boyd and Griffin, showed that 60% of PFN and 72% of PFNA patients had Type II fractures. Additionally, 32% of PFN and 16% of PFNA patients had Type III fractures, while 8% of PFN and 12% of PFNA patients had Type IV fractures.

The majority of surgeries in both groups had an operating time of 61–75 minutes. Among the complications observed, one patient in the PFN

group experienced Z-deformity, a known complication of intertrochanteric fracture treatment. Functional outcomes were assessed at each follow-up using the Harris Hip Score. At three months, the PFN group had an average score of 71.9 (range: 66–81), while the PFNA group had an average score of 74.87 (range: 66–81).

By six months, the PFN group's average score increased to 77.86 (range: 72–90), whereas the PFNA group's average score was 89.3 (range: 76–94). The improvement in functional outcomes was more pronounced in the PFNA group, and this difference was statistically significant ($p = 0.023$).

Table 1: Harris hip score

Average Score	PFN			PFNA		
	Type II	Type III	Type IV	Type II	Type III	Type IV
At 3 months	72.7	74	69	74.1	78.3	72.2
At 6 months	79.7	78.5	73	86.5	89.5	92.1
P value between group	0.023*					

Figure 1: Radiological images

Discussion

The therapy of unstable intertrochanteric fractures is complicated by osteoporosis impact on the prognosis.[11,12] Osteoporosis predicts screw migration in the proximal femur, leading to implant fail-

ure.[8,9] Clinical studies have also revealed a link between osteoporosis and poor intertrochanteric fracture outcomes.[9] Today's nail designs reflect the continued search for the best implant for these osteoporotic fractures. A helical blade device im-

proved fixation in these fractures. The helical blade was created for its biomechanical effectiveness in osteoporosis.[10]

The blade may be inserted without reaming, protecting femoral head bone stock. With greater purchase and resistance to varus collapse and rotational stress,[13] it compacts the cancellous bone surrounding it. Compared to normal PFN, this caused reduced clinical difficulties in an osteoporotic patient group. Because of the anticipated benefit of enhanced purchase in osteoporotic bone, the use of PFNA in older patients was commonly advocated in the current study.

This is why, although being similar on other parameters, the PFNA group was significantly older than the PFN group. Our data show PFNA has statistically significant differences in functional outcomes as determined by the Harris Hip Score between the two implants. The average age of our 50 patients with unstable intertrochanteric fracture was 47 years. This contrasts with the older age groups suggested by western literature. Our findings agree with those of RC Gupta et al.[13] and Mohanty SP et al.[14] Because Indians have a ten-year lower life expectancy than Westerners, and hunger and osteoporosis go hand in hand, the majority of instances occurred among the elderly.

The reason why the intertrochanteric area is the most prevalent location of fracture is most likely related to tensile osteoporosis as we age.[15] As a main joint in the weight-bearing system, the hip joint, which is already compromised, cannot sustain any unexpected aberrant force. The area between bone trabeculae enlarges and fills with fat, while dense tissue thins and calcar atrophies. In the current research, the male:female ratio was 18:7 for PFN and 16:9 for PFNA. In our research, there was a male sex predominance. The mechanism of injury was an unintentional fall, whereas 11 PFN and 13 PFNA patients were injured in a traffic collision. According to Horn and Wang,[16] the mechanism of damage is not direct, but rather the failure of stress resistant forces during abrupt bending or twisting. The average time between the injury and the operation was 9.6 days. The average operation time was calculated to be 67.7 minutes.[17] Our operating time was greater in the beginning, but as we gained expertise, it decreased. Boone and colleagues noted that the most prevalent kind of fracture was a type 2 fracture.[18] Our findings are consistent with earlier studies that compared these implant types. Mora A et al. compared the PFNA (helical blade) to the PFN and discovered that the PFNA had a lower cut-out rate.[19] Choo SK et al. reported that the PFNA had less postoperative sliding than the PFN,[20] discovered that helical blade nails significantly enhanced social function, mobility, and complication rates. In our study. Discovered that the probability of a late complication and re-

surgery is significantly higher with a PFN than with a helical blade device.

Conclusion

PFNA is an effective option for treating osteoporotic intertrochanteric fractures in elderly patients as it allows for a shorter surgical incision, reduced blood loss, and early rehabilitation, thereby decreasing both mortality and morbidity. PFNA also offers the advantages of reduced radiation exposure and greater stability, achieved through the helical blade's compaction of cancellous bone in the femoral head and mechanical impaction of the fracture. The primary drawback of PFNA is the relatively higher cost of the implant. Postoperative functional assessments at both three and six months have demonstrated superior outcomes with PFNA, with these improvements being statistically significant. However, it is important to emphasize that no implant design can compensate for inadequate fracture reduction or improper implant placement.

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